

SUPERSHINE

D6.2 – Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results – Part 2

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an updated version of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (CDEP), building upon the initial submission made at M6.

This deliverable presents a further analysis of SUPERSHINE’s Key Exploitable Results (KERs), describing their characteristics, ownership, and strategic value for post-project exploitation. The analysis highlights a strong replication potential across KERs, especially in relation to the business models, financial mechanisms (KER1), and the SUPERSHINE Portal (KER5), which several partners intend to scale through new collaborations, services, or follow-up projects. The integration of social acceptance models (KER3) and co-design approaches into institutional processes also emerges as a cross-cutting priority, supported by organizations such as ICONS, APRE and Housing Europe. Additionally, the chapter shows how technical KERs (KER2 and KER4) will be leveraged to enhance consulting services and capacity building, particularly by CIRCE, DEMIR and CARTIF.

A key focus is placed on KER5 – the **SUPERSHINE Portal**, identified as a central enabler for replication, stakeholder engagement, and the integration of multiple project outcomes. Partners plan to promote the Portal’s adoption across new cities and districts, with a strong emphasis on tailoring it to local contexts through co-design with stakeholders. The Portal includes four Sub-KERs: the **business model (5.1)**, **e-room (5.2)**, **training toolkit (5.3)**, and **one-stop shop (5.4)**. The **business model** underpins its long-term viability, enabling scalable revenue generation and strategic partnerships. The **e-room** is intended to support real-time project monitoring and data visualization, enhancing evidence-based decision-making. The **training toolkit** will be leveraged for replication and consulting purposes, particularly by CARTIF, while the **one-stop shop** will be commercialized via a dedicated legal entity (EEIG), targeting B2B and B2G markets with flexible subscription and licensing models.

The dissemination strategy for SUPERSHINE is designed with precision to target specific stakeholder groups at key stages of the project. We will deploy a range of communication tools tailored to each audience, ensuring that project outcomes are shared effectively and engagingly. This will include:

- Scientific publications and info packs that will communicate technical findings and innovations.
- Best practice books which will provide actionable insights and guidelines for practitioners.
- Policy briefs that will summarize key findings and recommend policy actions for stakeholders in governance and decision-making roles.
- Project final video which will visually showcase the project’s activities and impacts through interviews, on-site footage, and animations.
- A final event in Riga to present the project’s outcomes, provide networking opportunities, and share lessons learned.

To maximize the project’s impact, we will actively seek synergies by clustering collaboration strategies with other related initiatives. This will involve joining networks, organizing joint workshops, and co-hosting events with other projects focused on sustainable urban living and social housing. These collaborations will help broaden the reach of the project and facilitate the adoption of SUPERSHINE’s results.

Communication activities are strategically organized across multiple channels, including the project website, social media platforms, and timely publications, to ensure the consistent promotion of SUPERSHINE’s progress and key outcomes. These efforts aim to bolster the project's visibility while reinforcing its contribution to the transition toward sustainable urban living in Europe. A clear timeline aligns these activities with key milestones, ensuring that communication efforts remain synchronized with the project's broader objectives and deadlines.

1. Introduction

1.1. Introduction and integrated methodology

SUPERSHINE focuses on renovating social housing to reduce energy poverty and improve living conditions for households struggling with high energy bills. The project aims to create replicable models of smart, sustainable, and energy-efficient districts through three pilot lighthouse locations in Trieste (Italy), Herning (Denmark), and Riga (Latvia). SUPERSHINE seeks to drive the transition to zero-carbon living, supporting the European Green Deal and EU Renovation Wave Strategy, while expanding its models to additional cities across Europe, ultimately promoting sustainable lifestyles and resilience in urban areas.

A cohesive strategy for communication, dissemination, and exploitation is crucial to the success of the SUPERSHINE project. This approach enhances engagement throughout the project's duration and ensures that its outcomes have a lasting impact and practical application beyond the project's conclusion. By effectively communicating the project's objectives and achievements, sharing significant findings, and strategically planning the utilization of results, SUPERSHINE can amplify its influence and foster continuous progress in energy-intensive industries.

This deliverable constitutes an update to the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan Part 1, submitted at M6. It includes revised content reflecting advancements in Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) activities since the initial plan, maintaining focus on these key areas and synchronizing the strategy outlined therein with the progress made up to M29. CDE activities will undergo continuous update and refinement as SUPERSHINE progresses, feeding into the upcoming Report on dissemination and communication activities, including impact analysis (D6.4) and Final Exploitation Plan (D6.5), both due at M41.

The below image provides a visual summary of the methodological steps necessary to implement the strategy.

1.2. Structure of the deliverable

The document is structured in five main chapters, each providing specific insights into the project's Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategy, as outlined below:

Chapter 1 – Introduction - This chapter introduces the SUPERSHINE project, presents the integrated Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy, and explains how this document updates the initial CDE plan to reflect current progress.

Chapter 2 – SUPERSHINE KERs and Exploitation Strategies - It outlines the Key Exploitable Results (KERs), describes the tailored exploitation strategies developed by partners, and identifies key stakeholders to ensure long-term impact beyond the project's duration.

Chapter 3 – Dissemination Strategy - This section presents the dissemination approach, mapping stakeholder groups, linking each KER to specific dissemination actions, and detailing the tools used to ensure effective knowledge sharing.

Chapter 4 – Communication Activity - It highlights the communication channels used to promote the project, including the website, social media, publications, and videos, and provides a timeline for upcoming actions to boost outreach and visibility.

Chapter 5 – Conclusions - This chapter summarizes the updated CDE strategy, highlighting how it supports the visibility, replication, and sustainability of project results, while setting the stage for the final year's activities.

2. SUPERSHINE KERs and exploitation strategies

2.1. Methodology and process

This chapter offers an up-to-date view into Key Exploitable Results (KERs) developed by SUPERSHINE partners, detailing their characteristics, Intellectual Property ownership and measures and exploitation intentions for leveraging results to maximize the impact of the project after its conclusion.

KERs are critical outcomes characterized by high potential for utilization beyond the project’s timeframe and scope, and as such they include both tangible and intangible results, such as methodologies, technologies, products, models, platforms, data or knowledge. Exploitation strategies aim to ensure long-term sustainability and continued use of results developed within SUPERSHINE after the project’s end, including direct exploitation by Consortium partners and use by external stakeholders and other third parties.

Steps taken in the exploitation process after submission of D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1 are summarized in the following table. Next steps will include additional one-to-one interviews and input requests, as well as a final exploitation workshop, which will feed into D6.5 Final Exploitation Plan (M41): refer to 2.3 Exploitation intentions by partners for further information.

Table 1: SUPERSHINE’s exploitation process and timeframe

Exploitation process	Timeframe
D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1	M11
Setting up the Library of KERs and stakeholder mapping methodology	M12-M14
Distribution of Library of KERs & Stakeholder Mapping questionnaires	M15
One-to-one calls, analysis of data and inputs, prioritization and mapping exercise	M15-M18
D6.3 Library of KERs and Stakeholder Mapping	M19
Continuous updates	M19-M27
Workshop on the SUPERSHINE Portal at the Copenhagen GA	M25
Updating of KERs and exploitation intentions	M28

2.2. KERs and exploitation intentions

SUPERSHINE’s KERs and underlying sub-KERs are presented in the following table, starting from the detailed description of Key Exploitable Results produced for D6.3 Library of KERs and Stakeholder Mapping.

Table 2: SUPERSHINE’s KERs

KER	Title
KER1	Blueprint business and financial models and evaluation methodology
Sub-KER1.1	Financial profitability and cost reduction KPIs
Sub-KER1.2	Funding sources KPIs
Sub-KER1.3	Energy Poverty KPIs
Sub-KER1.4	Innovative Revenue Generation Models
Sub-KER1.5	Sustainability Impact Assessment Framework
Sub-KER1.6	Real estate crowdfunding strategy
KER2	Blueprint SLCA, LCA and LCC models
KER3	Blueprint social acceptance and co-design models
Sub-KER3.1	Guidelines on tenants’ engagement
KER4	Blueprint Technologies
KER5	SUPERSHINE Portal
Sub-KER5.1	SUPERSHINE Business Model
Sub-KER5.2	SUPERSHINE e-room
Sub-KER5.3	SUPERSHINE Training Toolkit
Sub-KER5.4	SUPERSHINE One-Stop Shop
KER6	Lighthouse, Fellow cities and supporting partners advancements in knowledge

The upcoming sub-chapters first offer a quick look into the characteristics of each result, then detailing the exploitation strategies that will be pursued in the post project phase to maximize the impact of the SUPERSHINE project. The five exploitation pillars upon which strategies are built are briefly reported in the table below.

Table 3: SUPERSHINE’s exploitation pillars

Exploitation pillars
Replication and upscaling of successful project implementations
Post project sustainability
Upscaling of Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
Commercialization of results and products/services developed
Academic and research exploitation

For each KER, the prioritised stakeholder groups are also identified, along with how their roles inform the tailoring of exploitation pathways and dissemination activities, based on the stakeholder mapping provided in D6.3.

2.2.1. KER1

Figure 1: KER1 overview

KER1 - Blueprint business and financial models and evaluation methodology

Comprehensive evaluation of financing options for energy efficiency renovations, considering both financial and socio-economic factors and providing insights into revenue generation, cost optimization, risk management, and performance evaluation.

<p> Marketability: Commercial and Non-commercial</p>	
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Overall, the University of York (UoY) plans to exploit the blueprint business and financial models and evaluation methodology through the following main strategies:

- **Replicating successful project implementations** in other cities and districts, upscaling the methodology for broader application in lighthouses districts.
- **Commercializing financial mechanisms and models developed**, as well as services created or enhanced through the knowledge generated during the project.
- **Contributing to academic and research endeavours** in the field.

These will be assessed more in detail for each of the Sub-KERs presented next, which all together constitute KER1.

The following table presents SUPERSHINE’s stakeholders that can play a particularly significant role toward the exploitation of KER1, together with their role in this process.

Table 4: Stakeholders prioritized for the exploitation of KER1

Stakeholder	Role
Public and private providers of social housing	TARGETS
EU and local financing institutions	SUPPLIERS/TARGETS
ESCOs	BENEFICIARIES
Housing associations and national and regional federations	SUPPORTERS/PARTNERS
Research stakeholders (academia, RTOs, technical experts)	SUPPORTERS/PARTNERS

2.2.1.1. Sub-KER1.1

Figure 2: Sub-KER1.1 overview

Sub-KER1.1 - Financial profitability and cost reduction KPIs

KPIs for EE renovations in social housing: Return on Investment, Net Present Value, Payback Period, and operating costs reduction.

 Type: KPIs

 TRL (M29 to M41): NA

 IP foreground owner: UoY

 IP measures: Copyright

Accessibility: Open

 Marketability: Commercial and Non-commercial

Exploitation strategies for the financial profitability and cost reduction Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) foreseen by the University of York resemble the three routes described for KER1. This includes: i) Replicating SUPERSHINE implementations in additional cities and districts, upscaling the methodology and approach of the project; ii) Commercializing the financial KPIs developed; and iii) Contributing to pursue further research and enhance academic curricula in the field.

2.2.1.2. Sub-KER1.2

Figure 3: Sub-KER1.2 overview

With regard to funding sources KPIs, two main lines of action are envisaged by the University of York in the post-project phase:

- Develop financial models for attracting investments in energy-efficient renovation projects in social housing. This will involve creating partnerships with financial institutions, analysing market trends, and implementing strategies to maximize Return on Investment (ROI) for investors.
- Replicate successful funding models in other EU countries, expanding the reach of energy-efficient renovation projects in social housing. Collaboration with local authorities, stakeholders, and financial institutions will be instrumental to adapting funding mechanisms and ensuring scalability of the SUPERSHINE approach.

In addition, the result will be leveraged to continue research on the topic, issue scientific publication and enrich university curricula. Depending on the outcomes of the project and on market demand, UoY will also consider providing consulting services grounded upon the expertise gained throughout the project.

2.2.1.3. Sub-KER1.3

Figure 4: Sub-KER1.3 overview

Sub-KER1.3 - Energy Poverty KPIs

KPIs on: i) monetary savings from EE renovations; ii) impact of renovations on energy poverty; iii) energy use efficiency in renovated units; iv) financial impact of renovations; v) effectiveness of renovations in terms of energy access; vi) impact of renovations on energy disconnection rates.

IP measures: Copyright	
TRL (M29 to M41): NA	Accessibility: Open
Marketability: Commercial and Non-commercial	

In the context of replication and upscaling, the following are among the main routes the University of York will consider pursuing after the end of the project for effective exploitation of Sub-KER1.3:

1. Guide stakeholders in making informed financial decisions, justify future investments, and assess the economic impact of sustainability initiatives
2. Observe the impact of energy efficient (EE) renovations on energy poverty
3. Evaluate the success of energy efficiency initiatives
4. Assess the financial impact of EE renovations
5. Ensure improved energy access for residents.

In order to operationalize these ambitions and enable effective use of energy poverty KPIs, activities to be undertaken will include data collection, financial and non-financial analysis, and dissemination of findings to stakeholders.

As for Sub-KER1.2, UoY will moreover employ the KPIs for producing scientific publications, furthering research and enriching university courses, projects and curricula. The use of KPIs and related knowledge to develop new or enhanced consulting services may also be taken into consideration, in accordance with SUPERSHINE’s results and with market assessments.

2.2.1.4. Sub-KER1.4

Figure 5: Sub-KER1.4 overview

Sub-KER1.4 - Innovative Revenue Generation Models

Innovative revenue generation models tailored for social housing renovation projects, incorporating concepts such as performance-based contracting, energy service agreements, and community financing, customized for SUPERSHINE's target regions.

<p>IP measures: Copyright Accessibility: Open</p>	
<p>Marketability: Commercial and Non-commercial</p>	
<p>IP foreground owners: AYMING, DEMIR, UoY, CIRCE, APRE</p>	

With the aim of enabling replication and upscaling of successful SUPERSHINE implementations, AYMING, DEMIR, UoY, CIRCE and APRE will maximize the impact of innovative revenue generation models through:

- Industry workshops, webinars, and online platforms to facilitate adoption by stakeholders involved in social housing renovation projects across Europe
- Engagement of and collaboration with key stakeholders, including local governments, housing associations, financial institutions, and community organizations, to promote implementation
- Case studies and real-world demonstrations showcasing the effectiveness and viability of models, to drive their integration into existing renovation projects and policies.

Furthermore, partners will collaborate with academic institutions and research organizations to conduct studies and evaluations that highlight the economic and social benefits of the models developed. The insights generated will inform policy decisions and feed into further research efforts, contributing to the advancement of sustainable urban development practices in Europe.

APRE will in particular evaluate the integration of the innovative revenue generation models into training courses and services for knowledge transfer and capacity building to members of its network. As a non-profit, quasi-public entity, APRE operates primarily along the lines of training and capacity building for its members (and beyond), with all services provided against the payment of administrative fees, in line with its non-commercial status. Consequently, it cannot directly exploit results for commercial revenue (e.g. through a one-stop-shop model), which requires careful consideration regarding its involvement in such activities. However, projects with a high degree of transferability can be valorised and integrated into APRE’s offer, thanks to dedicated internal units—namely “Valorizzazione” and “Formazione e nuovi servizi”—that assess the relevance and applicability of project outcomes and study how to embed them into the organization’s services.

These units, in close collaboration with the “Soci” unit (targeting APRE’s members), will play a key role in translating results into training and capacity building offerings. In addition, APRE’s “Progettazione” unit, responsible for identifying and drafting new proposals, can also support further exploitation through follow-up projects (as was the case with SUPERSHINE building on SUPER-i). As Italian National Contact Point for Horizon Europe, the organization holds the necessary capacity and expertise to promote implementation of the models through engagement of key stakeholders and by supporting scientific and institutional communities.

The innovative revenue generation models can be directly included in the SECAP plans to directly support the implementation of the technologies – as part of the financial analysis – and they may also be leveraged to enhance partners’ service offerings and capacity to support municipalities in future projects and be marketed as a stand-alone service.

2.2.1.5. Sub-KER1.5

Figure 6: Sub-KER1.5 overview

This result will first of all guide sustainability assessments in fellow cities. Partners will actively engage with policymakers, urban planners, and environmental organizations to advocate for the integration of the framework into policy frameworks and regulatory mechanisms at both local and European levels. By providing evidence-based assessments of sustainability impacts, SUPERSHINE aims to inform decision-making and shape future urban development strategies, all the while fostering uptake of project implementations and approach.

Additionally, AYMING, DEMIR and CIRCE will collaborate with academic institutions to develop training programs and educational materials that incorporate the framework’s principles and methodologies. Furthermore, the University of York will directly employ the result to guide further research and enhance educational initiatives related to sustainable urban development. These educational initiatives will help build capacity and expertise among stakeholders, ensuring the long-term sustainability of urban development efforts in Europe.

Similarly to Sub-KER1.4, APRE will assess the opportunity to integrate the sustainability impact assessment framework into training courses and services and give rise to follow-up projects, and other partners may as well integrate the framework into their strategy and service offering.

2.2.1.6. Sub-KER1.6

Figure 7: Sub-KER1.6 overview

The real estate crowdfunding strategy will be leveraged to replicate the implementation of SUPERSHINE in fellow cities and to upscale the interventions in lighthouse districts.

To this aim, TENDER anticipates enacting the following steps for each implementation:

1. Preparing a business plan, estimating costs, revenues, and timelines
2. Investigating the urban planning process, including checking whether building permits have already been obtained
3. Building design status analysis
4. Carrying out due diligence processes (technical, environmental and fiscal due diligence)
5. Conducting an assessment of Special Purpose Vehicle's (SPV) corporate documents (financial statements, chamber of commerce visas, bylaws, etc.).

Additionally, TENDER aims to operationalize and employ the strategy to launch a real estate funding platform, leveraging the knowledge acquired throughout the project in its development and go-to-market strategy. They will cooperate with local partners throughout the different European countries, due to the local nature of crowdfunding platforms. In each country and site, agreements will also be established with national and local ESCOs to facilitate obtaining refunds from municipalities for the energy savings achieved.

More detailed information on the crowdfunding strategy will be available as the development of underlying financial models is approaches its completion.

2.2.2. KER2

Figure 8: KER2 overview

KER2 - Blueprint SLCA, LCA and LCC models

Methodology to measure and manage the environmental, social and economic impact of lighthouse districts, identifying areas of improvement to alleviate the energy poverty of their citizens.

<p> Marketability: Commercial and Non-commercial</p>	
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The main exploitation routes envisaged for KER2 are two:

- **Replication of project implementations** towards fellow cities and upscaling in lighthouse districts
- **Product/service development** based on knowledge generated.

With respect to the first pathway, DEMIR will employ the blueprint SLCA, LCA and LCC models to facilitate upscaling and replication both in the cities identified during the project and in additional cities outside SUPERSHINE’s scope, possibly in the context of other funded projects involving local municipalities. Broad replication across Turkey, the EU and the UK will be supported by the development of City Climate Contracts (CCCs), enabled through the harmonization of various blueprint models. In doing this, DEMIR will leverage their established experience in collaborating with Mission cities (presently, Istanbul and Izmir) on CCCs.

As regards commercial exploitation, both CIRCE and DEMIR will leverage the expertise gained from the project to develop new or enhanced products or services.

On the one hand, CIRCE will offer an analysis service encompassing a comprehensive assessment of social, economic and/or environmental factors. Such a service will be made available to other districts – thus also aiding replication and upscaling efforts – by developing customized analyses tailored to their specific needs. These will detail the impacts and resources involved in each phase and will also be complemented by a consultancy service able inform evidence-based decision-making.

On the other hand, DEMIR will consider offering a consulting service with the aim of providing strategic advice to market parties that may lack the necessary skills and require guidance to measure and manage the environmental, social and economic impact of lighthouse districts, including on local aspects. This could translate into SECAP (Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan) support, within which DEMIR may replicate blueprint models, ICONS may be involved for social aspects, and

CARTIF for technological implementation. In the long-term, a next step could entail working with Mission cities’ contractors to provide LCA assessments to municipalities.

Stakeholder groups which are to be prioritised in order to maximize the exploitation potential of KER2 are included in the table below, together with the role they may play in this context.

Table 5: Stakeholders prioritised for the exploitation of KER2

Stakeholder	Role
European institutions and agencies, national governments, Local authorities, and bodies	ENABLERS
Public and private providers of social housing	TARGETS
National federations and housing associations	SUPPORTERS
Research & Academia, RTOs and technical experts	SUPPORTERS/PARTNERS

2.2.3. KER3

Figure 9: KER3 overview

KER3 - Blueprint social acceptance and co-design models

Blueprint for creating a validated and agreed-upon co-design model of the engagement strategy, aligning project outputs with their needs and enhancing societal acceptance of the proposed solutions, offering a solid framework for adaptation and replication.

<p> Marketability: Non-commercial</p>	
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With respect to the post project use of blueprint social acceptance and co-design models, ICONS plans to first of all refine their methodology based on insights gained from ongoing and future EU-funded projects, all the while **upsaling the blueprint’s Technology Readiness Level**. This process – and the research therein – will enhance the flexibility of the methodology, which may then be adapted for use in diverse contexts such as construction, marine platforms, and urban renovation, among others.

Moreover, ICONS aims to directly integrate the results into city-level initiatives for social housing renovation, supporting **replication and upsaling** activities. This involves a cyclic process of applying,

learning from, and adapting the models, once again increasing the value and impact of SUPERSHINE outcomes across different sectors and projects.

APRE will employ the blueprint as a strategic tool to enhance the design of engagement and co-creation activities carried out within training sessions, capacity building courses, workshops, and stakeholder events. These activities are core components of APRE’s mission and are implemented across a wide variety of formats and perspectives, with a strong focus on social innovation. In this context, APRE pays particular attention to initiatives such as the New European Bauhaus (NEB) and the Built4People partnership, where co-creation and citizen engagement approaches are central. The organization is committed to embedding these models into the design and delivery of future projects and training programmes and positioning the blueprint as a cross-cutting tool for added value and replication in other initiatives.

Although the overall engagement strategy was developed by ICONS, APRE’s role will be that of a key multiplier, implementing the strategy within its community and extending its impact at the European level. APRE also aims to promote the institutional uptake of these models by advocating for their integration into policymaking processes – for example, through ongoing collaboration with ATER Trieste and regional authorities. Furthermore, APRE is currently engaged in exploring and testing the Societal Readiness Level (SRL) framework, particularly within Horizon Europe Cluster 5 projects. While the SRL concept is still evolving, APRE is positioning itself to contribute to its definition and application, using the blueprint as a reference for piloting societal engagement methodologies – both within Cluster 5 and in other research and innovation contexts. Through this work, APRE leverages its network and internal expertise to connect diverse actors, foster community-based research practices, and support the institutionalisation of engagement and co-creation approaches as permanent tools for inclusive innovation.

Table 6: Stakeholders prioritized for the exploitation of KER3

Stakeholder	Role
Public and private providers of social housing	TARGETS
Technical stakeholders (ESCOs, construction & refurbishment service providers, energy efficiency solutions providers, engineering companies, HW/SW providers for the housing sector)	BENEFICIARIES
Consumers, prosumers and tenants	BENEFICIARIES
National and regional federations and housing associations	ENABLERS/SUPPORTERS

2.2.3.1. Sub-KER3.1

Figure 10: Sub-KER3.1 overview

Sub-KER3.1 - Guidelines on tenants' engagement

Guidelines to support practitioners in involving tenants, collecting their preferences and ideas and assessing their satisfaction level before and after interventions aimed at making renovation processes more inclusive.

<p> Marketability: Non-commercial</p>	
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In the post project, the efforts of Housing Europe (HE) will be directed toward utilizing the guidelines on tenants' engagement with the objective of replicating successful SUPERSHINE implementations in other cities and upscaling them in lighthouse districts, fostering wide adoption. Among the actions aimed at achieving this objective, HE intends to widely disseminate the guidelines among its members – leveraging social media platforms and website for broad outreach – and to identify synergies to integrate these guidelines with blueprints from other projects, enhancing their utility and applicability.

Additionally, Housing Europe will evaluate the development of new products or services based on the accumulated knowledge.

2.2.4. KER4

Figure 11: KER4 overview

KER4 - Blueprint technologies

Inventory of the technologies applied and tested within the SUPERSHINE project.

<p> Marketability: Commercial and Non-commercial</p>	
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Exploitation strategies for KER4 will be centred around two routes:

- **Replication of project implementations** towards fellow cities and upscaling in lighthouse districts
- **Product/service development** based on knowledge generated.

With respect to the first route, CIRCE and CARTIF plan to leverage this inventory to foster the replication of EE renovations in social housing. This will not only facilitate knowledge sharing but also enhance the decision-making process, by providing detailed insights into the effectiveness of different technologies. CARTIF, in particular, will continue directly supporting cities in the implementation of the technologies.

As regards the second pathway, strategies are more dependent on partners’ characteristics and operational context, and therefore more tailored to their needs and expectations:

- CIRCE will leverage this inventory for enhancing existing services such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA), and other energy efficiency analyses. By integrating advice on new technologies – based on the comprehensive inventory data – into their service offerings, CIRCE can provide clients with customized recommendations on the most advantageous and beneficial technologies to employ in each context.
- CARTIF is also considering employing the outcomes of KER4 to enhance their existing services and, eventually, to launch new services dedicated to the support of EE renovations in social housing.
- Housing Europe intends to develop a set of guidelines presenting the different technologies that can be deployed for a renovation to achieve diverse goals (e.g., improving energy efficiency, reducing waste, decreasing nuisances for tenants, improving biodiversity, etc.). The feasibility of each technology will be taken consideration, depending on the context of interest and thus taking into account differences such as climate, housing tenures, and regulations. The guidelines will be disseminated to the HE network of social housing providers, in synergy with other demonstrator projects of the Affordable Housing Initiative (AHI), which produced similar results but with different focus. The complementarity of the materials will be highlighted to showcase the multi-faceted approach to renovation of the AHI. The vectors for these activities will mainly be online and in-person events (including the final conference, workshops, other projects’ events), the SUPERSHINE portal and social media.

Table 7: Stakeholders prioritized for the exploitation of KER4

Stakeholder	Role
European institutions and agencies, national governments, Local authorities, and bodies	ENABLERS
Public and private providers of social housing	TARGETS

Technical stakeholders (ESCOs, energy efficiency solutions providers, engineering companies, HW/SW providers for the housing sector, technical experts)	SUPPLIERS/PARTNERS
Research stakeholders (academia, RTOs)	SUPPORTERS/PARTNERS

2.2.5. KER5

Figure 12: KER5 overview

KER5 - SUPERSHINE Portal

Innovative online portal that integrates a unique combination of services including data collection (e-room), training materials, and matchmaking, tailored for public authorities, real estate developers, and landlords. It aims to drive systemic changes in governance by enhancing systems thinking, analyzing interconnections within systems, and pinpointing strategic interventions to optimize outcomes. As the central communication hub for the project, it also serves as the European reference point, showcasing project results and connecting enterprises, stakeholders, and both institutional and private investors. This support extends to hosting training materials and tools such as the OSS and supporting crowdfunding campaigns, building on the legacy of the SUPER-i portal.

<p> Marketability: Commercial and Non-commercial</p>	
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The Consortium’s exploitation intentions for the SUPERSHINE Portal are aimed to maximize its reach and impact, making it a pivotal tool in urban transformation processes. By promoting the Portal across various cities and districts and by replicating successful implementations, partners will ensure its adoption on a broad scale and will amplify the overall impact of the SUPERSHINE initiative.

Three interrelated strategies will be pursued, both with regard to KER5 and underlying Sub-KERs, which will be presented next:

- **Upscaling of technology TRLs and commercialization**
- **Replication of project implementations** towards fellow cities and upscaling in lighthouse districts
- **Sustainability plan** of the SUPERSHINE Portal.

As successful implementation of the strategies is interdependent, a comprehensive roadmap to operationalize these ambitions in the post project phase can be articulated in the following steps:

1. Target identification: Determining potential target cities and districts, based on factors such as urban development priorities, readiness for innovation, and existing partnerships.
2. Stakeholder engagement: Initiating dialogue with local government officials, urban planners, community leaders, and other key stakeholders to gauge interest and secure commitment to the SUPERSHINE initiative.
3. Portal customization: Collaborating closely with local stakeholders to tailor the SUPERSHINE Portal to specific local conditions, including regulatory frameworks and infrastructural considerations.
4. Monitoring and evaluation: Establishing mechanisms to monitor the implementation and evaluate the impact of pilot projects, incorporating feedback from users and stakeholders to refine the approach.
5. Knowledge sharing: Gathering and distributing documentation, case studies, and best practice guides through channels such as conferences, workshops, and publications to share insights and promote learning.
6. Scaling up: Expanding successful implementations to additional cities and districts, utilizing established partnerships and networks to facilitate wider dissemination.
7. Sustainability planning: Developing comprehensive sustainability plans to secure the long-term success and impact of implementations, focusing on funding, governance, and ongoing stakeholder engagement.

Table 8: Stakeholders prioritized for the exploitation of KER5

Stakeholder	Role
Public and private providers of social housing	TARGETS
Eu and local financing institutions	SUPPLIERS/PARTNERS
National and regional federations and housing associations	PARTNERS/SUPPORTERS
Research stakeholders (academia, RTOs, technical experts)	BENEFICIARIES/PARTNERS

2.2.5.1. Sub-KER5.1

Figure 13: Sub-KER5.1 overview

This SUPERSHINE business model is aimed at ensuring that each step in the post project exploitation of the One-Stop Shop (OSS; Sub-KER5.4) – from initial research to revenue generation – is carefully planned and executed.

The main exploitation route for the business model lies within the sustainability plan of the SUPERSHINE Portal, with three main goals:

- **Scalability:** Replicating and adapting the SUPERSHINE business model across various contexts and locations, enhancing its scalability.
- **Market expansion:** Broadening the reach of the SUPERSHINE initiative through strategic partnerships and collaborations with stakeholders in new cities, districts, and regions.
- **Revenue generation:** Establishing sustainable revenue streams by commercializing the SUPERSHINE business model, ensuring long-term viability and expansion of the initiative.

In this view, the following are among key activities that will be undertaken:

1. **Market research:** Identifying potential markets and assessing their compatibility with the SUPERSHINE business model, focusing on those areas which are most likely to benefit from and contribute to its success.
2. **Partnership development:** Forging strategic alliances with local governments, organizations, and businesses to facilitate the replication process and garner support.
3. **Business model customization:** Tailoring the business model to meet specific local regulatory, market, and stakeholder requirements, ensuring it fits within each new environment.
4. **Pilot implementation:** Executing pilot projects to validate the adapted business model in real-world scenarios, collect data, and solicit feedback, focusing on critical metrics like user adoption, revenue potential, and stakeholder satisfaction.

5. Scaling up: Expanding successful models to additional markets and regions, utilizing established partnerships and networks to amplify reach and impact.
6. Revenue strategies: Developing and implementing localized revenue strategies, exploring diverse routes (including licensing, subscription models, or service fees) to secure financial stability and growth.

2.2.5.2. Sub-KER5.2

Figure 14: Sub-KER5.2 overview

The e-room is foreseen as an interactive data within the Portal hub that facilitates real-time analysis of social housing projects, serving as a repository which enables flexible data collection and leverages visualization functionalities.

The post project exploitation strategy for the SUPERSHINE e-room will revolve around two pathways:

- Replication of project implementations towards fellow cities and upscaling in lighthouse districts, by offering a platform and resources for enhanced knowledge dissemination, facilitated engagement, and evidence-based decision-making
- Academic and research exploitation, further developing project results and supporting their uptake.

2.2.5.3. Sub-KER5.3

Figure 15: Sub-KER5.3 overview

Sub-KER5.3 - SUPERSHINE Training toolkit

Full capacity building model for increasing competences and skills, leveraging and systematizing the onsite physical workshops and considering different perspectives: i) organizational and executive; ii) human resources; iii) residents. It includes a methodology for identifying cities’ needs and knowledge and partners’ expertise and technical profile, and it will be integrated in the SUPERSHINE Portal.

<p> Marketability: Commercial and Non-commercial</p>	
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First and foremost, the training toolkit will be leveraged by project partners to support the replication of successful SUPERSHINE implementations in the fellow and other cities and to upscale lighthouse districts. It will provide capacity building to support further implementations in vulnerable districts, enabling an assessment of the viability of interventions, of cities’ needs and knowledge, of partners’ expertise and technical profile, and of the resulting gaps. The Toolkit, which will be part of the SUPERSHINE Portal (KER5), is also intended to be leveraged by external entities that may need support in similar implementations.

CARTIF will also leverage the knowledge acquired in the development of the Toolkit to perform further research on the topic, upgrade and upscale it through further (funded) projects. Lastly, CARTIF expects to employ the result as a knowledge basis to provide strategic guidance to entities that want to implement EE renovations. This may result in the provision of consulting services to municipalities, social housing associations and private and public providers of social housing, among potential target stakeholder groups.

2.2.5.4. Sub-KER5.4

Figure 16: Sub-KER5.4 overview

Sub-KER5.4 - SUPERSHINE One-Stop Shop

A comprehensive platform integrated within the SUPERSHINE Portal as a central hub for social housing managers and residents, to streamline and enhance EE refurbishment by offering a full renovation package with guaranteed energy savings and coordinating market actors involved. It operates as a single-entry point that manages and simplifies the information flow between governmental bodies, business partners, and customers, to harmonize refurbishment efforts at the district level.

<p> Marketability: Commercial and Non-commercial</p>	
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The SUPERSHINE One-Stop Shop will be commercialised through a well-structured approach aimed at supporting the transition of European social housing districts towards climate neutrality. The tool is currently under development, with CIRCE preparing a mock-up version to demonstrate its functionalities and potential. In the project’s final year (M30 to M41), Work Package 7 (WP7) will refine the business plan of the One-Stop Shop and establish a SUPERSHINE legal entity, specifically a European Economic Interest Group (EEIG). This structure has been chosen because it allows flexibility in financing, as it does not require shared capital but permits alternative financing methods.

The legal entity will consolidate resources and expertise from Consortium members in order to sustain economic balance over the mid- to long-term. Initially, EEIG members will finance capital expenditures with their own resources, aiming for self-sustainability. Financial strategies will at first depend on operational expenditures, covering the project-funded life before transitioning to the open market. For mid-term sustainability, a multi-annual budget will be crucial. The business model will anticipate potential market disruption – like those experienced during the COVID-19 pandemic – by planning a risk appraisal and due diligence in the project’s last year, with the aim of ensuring bankability and resilience.

The market entry strategy of the One-Stop Shop will include versatile business-to-government (B2G) and business-to-business (B2B) subscription models. These offer services to a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including public local authorities, professional users, and social housing managers, among others; as such, these models go beyond traditional Software as a Service (SaaS) models. Moreover, services will be made available through both direct subscriptions or licensing to third parties (B2B2C), ensuring flexibility to cater to various customer sizes and types.

Currently, project partners are also evaluating the potential of the One-Stop Shop to serve as a matchmaking platform, where technical entities—such as technology providers, construction firms, and developers—can connect with potential clients. In this scenario, the revenue model could be based on a percentage fee applied to contracts secured through the platform, or alternatively through sponsorship or listing fees paid by participating companies seeking visibility and business opportunities.

This plan aims to enable the entity to tap into the extensive market potential of climate-neutral transition processes, particularly in the social and affordable housing sectors. It promises comprehensive benefits such as simplification, cost reduction, easy management of intellectual property rights, and effective, transparent customer interactions. The business model supports systemic governance changes by promoting innovative, systems-thinking approaches to urban development and renovation, ensuring that all interventions lead to optimal outcomes. As such, this strategy promotes replication and upscaling of successful SUPERSHINE implementations in other cities and districts.

In addition, CIRCE – and all project partners in general – will evaluate opportunities to leverage the expertise gained throughout the development of the One-Stop Shop in further research endeavours.

2.2.6. KER6

Figure 17: KER6 overview

KER6 - Lighthouse, Fellow cities and supporting partners advancements in knowledge

Comprehensive knowledge exploitation framework of lessons learned and best practices from lighthouse and fellow cities and supporting partners, to enhance sustainable EU urban energy solutions. It spans EE innovations, stakeholder engagement models, business models and financial mechanisms, technology and infrastructure improvements, and environmental impact.

<p>IP measures: Know-how, Copyright</p>	
<p>TRL (M29 to M41): NA</p>	<p>Accessibility: Open (private for INSME knowledge on engagement and fundraising)</p>
<p>Marketability: Commercial and Non-commercial</p>	

The post project exploitation of the extensive body of knowledge KER6 is grounded upon includes three main routes:

- Further development and **upscaling of technology TRLs**

- **Replication of SUPERSHINE implementations** towards fellow cities and upscaling in lighthouse districts
- **Provision of new or enhanced commercial services**, leveraging the expertise gained.

The remainder of this subchapter will delve into the strategies which each owner of the Intellectual Property (IP) foreground associated with the result plans to deploy. As exploitation intentions widely vary from one context to another and the above routes are often implemented in pairs and interconnected, dedicated paragraphs are presented for each partner.

Faellesbo (FB) intends to make use of the knowledge generated during the project in order to replicate SUPERSHINE implementation in other FB housing departments. It will leverage all KERs to foster replication and upscaling of the implemented solutions and of the SUPERSHINE approach in general. More specifically:

- Blueprint business and financial models (KER1) and Blueprint SLCA, LCA and LCC models (KER2) may serve to expand the energy, environmental and building renovation measures that FB can finance and implement, as a supplement to the standard building renovation measures financed through Landsbyggefonden. This depends on the feasibility of using the blueprint in a Danish setting.
- Blueprint social acceptance and co-design models (KER3) will be employed as a tool for minimizing negative social impacts when carrying out building renovation activities.

Boligselskabernes Landsforening (BL) will also leverage the knowledge acquired in the project to support the replication of SUPERSHINE solutions in Danish contexts. BL holds up to 20% of the total social housing in Denmark and will rely on such extensive network to disseminate the project's concept and approach, as well as to favour its replication.

As a SUPERSHINE lighthouse city, **Riga Energy Agency** (REA) aims to upscale and replicate the EE renovation interventions in social housing in other districts of the city. Because the city of Riga has already identified the technologies to be implemented to renovate the buildings (mainly with respect to insulation and heating), the most relevant results for REA lie in the financial and business models to fund such interventions (KER1). Riga is characterized by a very high replication potential for such knowledge to foster renovations in other neighbourhoods, also due to the conditions of social housing. In fact, social housing is mainly located in around 4,000 "standard" soviet buildings which present very similar characteristics to the ones which are the object of the SUPERSHINE renovation interventions.

Azienda Territoriale per l'Edilizia Residenziale di Trieste (ATER) will leverage the knowledge acquired in the project to continue upscaling the renovations performed as a lighthouse city, as well as to support replication in other areas of Trieste and favour the uptake of SUPERSHINE solutions at a wider scale. In order to achieve this goal, ATER has already planned to organize a dedicated event to present the overall SUPERSHINE approach to Federcasa, who brings together 84 social housing entities and agencies in Italy, accounting for 83% of the national public residential stock¹.

¹ feder casa.it/chi-siamo/chi-siamo

Zaragoza Vivienda (ZV), as the municipal company responsible for public housing in Zaragoza, will employ the expertise obtained throughout the SUPERSHINE project in order to replicate the envisioned solutions, adopting the SUPERSHINE approach to implement EE efficient renovations in the buildings it manages. Furthermore, ZV will play a key role in fostering a broad uptake of the SUPERSHINE approach in the region.

Agência de Energia e Ambiente da Arrábida (ENA) also intends to leverage the knowledge acquired within the project to adapt and replicate the SUPERSHINE solutions towards EE social housing renovation. The roadmap ENA will follow to achieve this objective includes:

- Raising awareness and engaging target groups to create the necessary framework conditions for the implementation of the business and financial models (KER1). This will require coordinating with municipalities and social stakeholders, citizens representatives, and ethical banking entities.
- Optimizing results for usage in the ENA territory, which corresponds to the municipalities of Palmela, Sesimbra and Setúbal.
- Implementing the SLCA, LCA, LCC, and co-design models (KER2) in ENA's territory by disseminating the models to and engaging with municipalities, social stakeholders, social housing entities, and citizens representatives.
- Supporting technology implementation by analysing the blueprint to be applied in ENA's territory, through meetings with municipalities and social housing entities and by defining priorities with financial entities.
- Actively contributing to the sustainability of the SUPERSHINE Portal through dissemination and updating, and integrating it in ENA's activities.

Kadikoy Municipality (KM) will employ the knowledge acquired within SUPERSHINE to foster replication of EE renovations in social housing not only in Kadikoy and Istanbul districts, but across Turkey as a whole. This will be possible also by leveraging the Union of Municipalities, which brings together all the 81 city governments of Turkey. As regards the knowledge advancements related to specific KERs, KM will:

- Select and adapt the financial and business models (KER1) which best fit to the Turkish regulatory framework (e.g., ESCO models in Turkey are not suitable to foster energy efficient renovations), with the support of DEMIR.
- Foster the adoption and adaptation of SLCA, LCA, and LCC models (KER2) by providing guidance on their application.
- Develop and provide consultancy services, capacity-building workshops, tailored guidance and support, engagement with local businesses and organizations for knowledge transfer and implementation support. Collaboration with stakeholders will enable integration of blueprint models into CCC frameworks, advocacy for policy support, and dissemination of best practices.

- Work together with lighthouse districts for upscaling, knowledge sharing, and mutual support, as well as offer consultancy services leveraging expertise gained from the blueprint implementation.
- Collaborate with academic institutions to validate project effectiveness and develop new solutions.

Spacetime (SP) plans to employ the expertise gained in the SUPERSHINE project to foster the replication of social housing EE renovation in the Serbian context.

European Green Cities (EGC), given its role to bridge the gap between EU funding and local partners, will leverage the knowledge acquired within the SUPERSHINE project in order to provide support to such local entities, by engaging in new collaborations with Social Housing Operator or through the participation in further EU funded projects.

INSME aims to perform further research on the topics related to the project, issuing scientific publications and producing guidelines for environmental and social research. More specifically, activities will involve:

- Deepening the understanding of policies and regulatory frameworks, and innovative practices for the creation of smart neighbourhoods: Results will feed into a policy paper, to be promoted as guidelines for supporting businesses and companies engaged in innovation processes and technology transfer in the fields of environmental sustainability and social housing.
- Developing models for simplifying complex data into numerical terms through qualitative and quantitative research methods: The techniques used and the results of the research will be included in a report that would serve as a collection of best practices and suggestions for quantitative and qualitative methods of environmental and social research. The report will then be published in journals of the sector, including the International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health and the Open Environmental Research Journal, which INSME is currently evaluating.
- Working on techniques for engaging specific and diversified audiences, and for creating fundraising campaigns: The objective is to develop a consultancy service to increase audience involvement in European projects and fundraising operations. This service will be aimed at stakeholders, companies, associations, research institutes and government bodies that deal with planning specifically linked to sustainability and technological innovation to support them in the planning and formulation of the engagement strategy with the audience and in the creation of campaigns to the financing of project activities. The service will be organised through policy papers, training workshops and seminars to stimulate the establishment of engagement skills in the stakeholders involved.

2.3. Next steps for successful exploitation

As the project approaches its final year, emphasis will be placed on finalizing exploitation strategies and ensuring they are up to date with respect to both SUPERSHINE developments and changes in the external environment. Roadmaps for post-project exploitation will particularly focus on sustainability of the results and of the SUPERSHINE Portal.

Next steps will include additional, in-depth one-to-one interviews with Consortium partners, together with input requests and a final exploitation workshop, with the objective of refining and enhancing the level of detail in partner-level exploitation strategies. Furthermore, coordination with AYMING will be key to the integration of the work carried out for the development of a legal entity and business models for KER5 – the SUPERSHINE Portal – and its components toward the overall post-action sustainability.

Once KERs and both individual and joint intentions have been further consolidated and developed, these will then feed into the upcoming Final Exploitation Plan (D6.5, due at M41), turning strategies into actionable plans to maximize impact and sustainability of SUPERSHINE results.

3. Dissemination Strategy

3.1. Stakeholder analysis

The dissemination strategy presented in what follows is grounded upon previous work included in two project deliverables:

1. **D6.1 Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results - Part 1:** stakeholder groups and sub-groups are identified and a short profile is provided for each of them, including their reference market and operational context, along with their main interests in SUPERSHINE’s results
2. **D6.3 Library of Key Exploitable Results and Stakeholder Mapping:** starting from partners’ input and questionnaire responses, for each KER stakeholders are mapped into an impact/interest matrix and specific roles are assigned to every sub-group (supplier, partner, enabler, supporter, beneficiaries, target), providing significant insights for stakeholder engagement to maximise the impact of the results beyond the project.

SUPERSHINE’s stakeholder groups and stakeholders as defined in D6.1 are presented in the following table.

Table 9: SUPERSHINE's stakeholders

Group	Stakeholders
Policymakers and public authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European institutions and agencies • National governments, Local authorities, and bodies
Social housing organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public providers of social housing • Private providers of social housing
Financing institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local financing institutions • EU financing institutions
Construction and building industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction & Refurbishment services • Engineering companies
Technology services and products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HW/SW providers for the housing sector • Energy-efficiency technology companies
Energy companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ESCOs • Utility companies

Residents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tenants • Consumers • Prosumers
Associations, clusters, and membership organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Housing associations • National and regional federations
Scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academia • Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) • Technical experts
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National and European media

Among key takeaways that can be derived from the stakeholder mapping analysis:

- **Importance of continuous stakeholder engagement:** as the project progresses, maintaining open lines of communication with key stakeholders and adjusting strategies in response to feedback and evolving market conditions will be crucial for the sustained relevance of SUPERSHINE outcomes
- **Different stakeholders are to be prioritized for different results:** Key Exploitable Results differ in the stakeholder groups and sub-groups that should be the main target of dissemination and engagement activities: in this respect, public and private providers of social housing stand out as the only sub-group to be prioritized for all SUPERSHINE’s main KERs (1-5)
- **Need to develop tailored dissemination strategies:** targeted stakeholder engagement ensures greater impact, including by taking into account the roles played by stakeholders
- **Networking potential:** clusters, partnerships and networks are crucial to collaboration and outreach, amplifying support for SUPERSHINE’s initiatives and seizing opportunities for adoption and replication of project results.

3.2. KERs and dissemination strategy

3.2.1. Infopacks

The consortium has scheduled the creation of four information packs designed as visually engaging fact sheets, info sheets, or concise reports. These materials aim to provide the professional community with insights into SUPERSHINE's technical solutions, achievements, findings, and developed measures. The content will be sourced from the project's public deliverables and scientific publications.

The production of these info packs is planned between September and December 2025. They will be distributed at scientific and technical events, made available for download on the project

website, and actively shared with key stakeholder groups interested in staying informed about project outcomes.

The table below outlines the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) identified as most suitable for dissemination through these info packs, based on stakeholder mapping and prioritization.

Name of KER	Stakeholders
KER1 Blueprint business and financial models and evaluation methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public and private providers of social housing EU and local financing institutions ESCOs
Sub-KER1.6 Real estate crowdfunding strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public and private providers of social housing EU and local financing institutions ESCOs Research stakeholders (academia, RTOs, technical experts)
KER3 Blueprint social acceptance and co-design models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public and private providers of social housing Technical stakeholders (ESCOs, construction & refurbishment service providers, energy efficiency solutions providers, engineering companies, HW/SW providers for the housing sector) Consumers, prosumers and tenants National and regional federations and housing associations
Sub-KER5.4 SUPERSHINE One-Stop Shop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public and private providers of social housing EU and local financing institutions National and regional federations and housing associations

3.2.2. Best Practice Handbook

SUPERSHINE Best Practices Handbook will serve as a comprehensive guide that showcases the project’s key achievements, best practices, lessons learned, and evidence-based recommendations. The main objective of the best practice handbook is to offer approaches and strategies to implement the project results.

The handbook is targeted at key stakeholder groups including technology providers, the construction sector, social housing organisations, and policy makers, supporting them in adopting and scaling up the project’s outcomes within their respective domains.

The handbook will reflect insights gathered from all stages of the SUPERSHINE project—ranging from development and testing through to the validation phase. This ensures that the content is grounded in real-world application and reflective of the full lifecycle of the project’s innovations. The publication will be made available in both electronic and printable formats to ensure wide accessibility and usability.

The development of the handbook will be a collaborative effort. Project partners will contribute the technical content and share their reflections on the lessons learned throughout implementation. ICONS, with the University of York (UoY) and APRE, will oversee the overall development process.

ICONS will lead the design, editing and final layout of the publication. In cases where content is particularly technical, designated partners or the project coordinator may be asked to draft specific sections, following a clear set of guidelines provided by ICONS.

The production of the handbook is planned between September and December 2025

3.2.3. Policy brief

SUPERSHINE will develop a policy brief to provide policymakers and relevant authorities with a clear and concise overview of key challenges and opportunities in social housing. The document will outline the project’s findings and propose actionable policy recommendations to support the integration of innovative financial and technical solutions into the social housing sector.

The policy brief will be published between May and June and the contents will be led by DEMIR, ensuring that its content is well-informed by SUPERSHINE’s research and deliverables.

The policy brief will consist of a general overview alongside a detailed analysis of social housing policies in the seven project countries. By examining regulatory, financial, and technical aspects, the document aims to inform decision-makers about the crucial role of inclusive urban planning, infrastructure modernization, and sustainable financing.

3.2.4. Project Video

The project video will be a carefully curated combination of footage from the three demo sites, integrating recordings provided by the Danish partner alongside additional filming conducted in Trieste and possibly Riga.

It will feature a blend of on-site visuals and interviews with key stakeholders, including the project coordinator, Riccardo Coletta, as well as other consortium partners, to provide valuable insights into the project’s impact and objectives.

To ensure a cohesive and engaging narrative, the video will also incorporate high-quality animations and graphics that align with the project’s visual identity.

The production process will take place throughout 2025, with the final version expected to be released within the year.

The video aims to showcase the project's impact, present insights from key stakeholders, and visually communicate its objectives through engaging footage and animations. Its target audience includes project stakeholders, industry professionals, and potential collaborators or supporters.

3.2.5. Final event

As the SUPERSHINE project enters its final phase, we are planning a two-step closing strategy to maximize impact and engagement:

- **October 2025 – Trieste, Italy:** A site visit will be organized to showcase key outcomes and insights from the project. A consortium meeting will also be optionally held in a hybrid format, allowing partners to discuss progress and next steps.
- **February/March 2026 – Riga, Latvia:** The Final Conference will take place, bringing together project partners and stakeholders to present the main results and impact of SUPERSHINE.

This dual approach aims to combine local impact with a broader dissemination strategy, reinforcing SUPERSHINE's contributions to sustainable and inclusive social housing.

3.3. Clustering collaboration strategy

Participating in project clustering and networking initiatives contributes to raising SUPERSHINE's profile, strengthening partnerships, and facilitating the exchange of expertise.

These collaborative efforts extend the project's reach but also pave the way for shared exploitation pathways and integration into a wider landscape of innovation.

SUPERSHINE has actively built connections with a number of EU-funded project and initiatives, such as **drOp**, **ProLight**, and **SHAPE EU**. Through collaborative efforts like joint newsletters, we've taken steps toward establishing a more coordinated framework for joint future dissemination and communication activities, such as:

- SUPERSHINE co-organised an interactive workshop during the 22nd European Week of Regions and Cities, held on 6 November. The session guided participating cities through the process of transforming social housing districts, with a strong focus on inclusion and sustainability. The workshop created dialogue among local authorities, policy makers, and

practitioners, while highlighting the approaches and solutions gathered from the knowledge generated for SUPERSHINE.

SUPERSHINE also joined the **Network of Building Renovation Projects**, an initiative launched to promote collaboration and create synergies in engaging stakeholders from the construction sector and applied research fields. The network brings together 18 Horizon Europe-funded projects with the shared goal of exchanging knowledge, showcasing solutions, coordinating joint events, and supporting one another's visibility across the sector.

In the coming months, SUPERSHINE will be involved in several exciting collaborative activities:

- As part of the International Social Housing Festival (ISHF) 2025, SUPERSHINE will join the ProLight sister project in participating in the final conference of the drOp project, titled "*More than Renovation: Neighbourhood Regeneration*"
- Additionally, as part of the ISHF, SUPERSHINE has been invited by the DEDALUS project to contribute to a seminar on "Innovating Communities: Exploring Drivers and Barriers of Public Engagement in Social Housing."

4. Communication Activity

4.1.1. Website

The SUPERSHINE website is the central reference point for all stakeholders involved in the project and it functions as an entry point to SUPERSHINE, designed to engage diverse target audiences including social housing organisations, the construction and building sector, financial institutions, technology providers, the scientific community, and the public.

The website is fully scalable and is regularly updated with fresh content.

All the contents published on the website are accessible to all viewers with no restrictions and friendly accessible from all types of devices (desktop, mobile).

In recognition of the close connection between SUPER-i and SUPERSHINE, both project consortia agreed to join forces and optimise efforts by sharing a single web platform. As a result, the existing SUPER-i website was restructured to integrate dedicated content for SUPERSHINE.

The updated website includes joint sections for news, events, and resources, while a clear labelling system was introduced to differentiate which content belonged to which project, including the homepage, redesigned to clearly and prominently represent both projects, allowing visitors to immediately recognise the collaborative nature of the initiative.

Since the launch of the SUPERSHINE and SUPER-i website, a total of **32,706 pageviews** have been registered, with 7,442 unique users actively engaging with the platform.

In the final year of the project, the website will serve as a platform to showcase the main results and dissemination materials, while being adapted to meet the specific needs of the consortium and the Key Exploitable Results (KER) management. The website will continue to be maintained and updated even after the project's conclusion, ensuring its long-term accessibility and relevance to all stakeholders involved.

4.1.2. Social Media Channels

SUPERSHINE has established a strong online presence, with LinkedIn serving as its primary social media platform. Given the project's focus on engaging professional and industrial stakeholders, including investors, LinkedIn was identified as the most effective channel for outreach.

In addition to LinkedIn, a Twitter/X account was created as a secondary platform to expand the project's reach to audiences beyond the professional sphere—such as journalists, citizens, and civil society organisations.

In July 2024, the SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE Twitter/X account was suspended. To further strengthen its visibility and connect with a broader audience after the suspension of the X/Twitter account, SUPERSHINE launched an official Facebook page in October 2024.

All platforms are actively managed and regularly updated with content generated internally and externally from the consortium, to engage users and attract new stakeholders to the project’s mission.

The table below represents the performance of the SUPERSHINE project across its main social media channels—X (formerly Twitter), LinkedIn, Facebook, and YouTube.

Table 10 : SUPERSHINE Social Media Channels Performance

	Followers	Number of Posts	Total Engagement	Total Outreach
X/Twitter (before suspension)	656	213	3,858	44,924
LinkedIn	467	119	4,855	41,734
Facebook	30	25	540	1,715
YouTube	3	7	531	1,298
Total	1,186	364	9,784	89,671

The graphs below represent where the total outreach and engagement stem from SUPERSHINE's social media activities over time.

Table 11 : SUPERSHINE Engagement and Outreach Trend Graphs

Peaks in monthly engagement are visible in March 2023, and especially October 2024, which reflects the project's most successful month in terms of audience interaction.

The right graph displays cumulative outreach, tracking the number of people reached through SUPERSHINE’s social media content. Major spikes occurred in Summer 2023, and December 2024, indicating targeted communication pushes or milestone campaigns that effectively captured attention.

Since the launch of the project, SUPERSHINE has carried out two social media campaigns in 2024, which align with the peaks seen in both engagement and outreach trends.

The first was the campaign for the EU Sustainable Energy Week (EUSEW), and the second was the "SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE: Dialogues Under the Spotlight" Interview Series—both of which significantly boosted the project’s visibility and audience interaction.

In the final year of the project, the social media channels will play a key role in communicating the project’s key results and achievements, engaging with a broader audience, and fostering ongoing dialogue. These platforms will be used not only to share the outcomes but also to reinforce collaboration and networking within the community, ensuring continued engagement and support for the project’s legacy. Additionally, the channels will help to expand the project’s reach, connecting new stakeholders and ensuring the community remains active and growing even after the project's conclusion.

4.1.3. Publications

The publications, serving as the editorial covers of SUPERSHINE's activities, are essential in communicating the project's achievements and updates. They have remained consistently active from the beginning of the project until its conclusion, ensuring continuous visibility, transparency, and engagement with stakeholders and the broader public.

Since the beginning of SUPERSHINE, 25 publications have been recorded, and the table below represents the publications by type:

Table 12: SUPERSHINE Publications by type

The total outreach of 26,324 and engagement of 1,440 generated by the publications reflect their significant contribution to SUPERSHINE’s overall communication impact.

The tables below represent how each type of publication has contributed to the cumulative outreach and engagement, highlighting the effectiveness of various editorial formats in reaching and involving the audience throughout the project.

4.1.3.1. Journalistic Article

Here is a table summarizing the publication details, including outreach and engagement metrics for a recent article on citizen-led initiatives in decentralization, sustainability, and energy democratization.

Table 13 : SUPERSHINE Journalistic Article Outreach and Engagement

	Publication Date	Average Outreach	Average Engagement
<u>Decentralisation, sustainability and energy democratisation. The untapped potential of citizen-led initiatives</u>	07/02/2024	15,527	375

SUPERSHINE will produce a second journalistic article in 2025.

4.1.3.2. News Releases

Here is a table presenting the outreach and engagement metrics for SUPERSHINE news releases, highlighting key events and initiatives.

Table 14 : SUPERSHINE News Releases Outreach and Engagement

	Publication Date	Average Outreach	Average Engagement
SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE at the 4th International Social Housing Festival Highlights	6/24/2023	291	9
Shaping Tomorrow Together: Surveys for Lighthouse Owners, Managers, Residents	2/1/2024	262	n/a
SUPERSHINE Lighthouse Districts: Pave the Way for Sustainable Urban Living	2/15/2024	618	30
SUPERSHINE AT TRIESTE: A New way of Sustainable Living	6/26/2024	713	195
Updates from Our Lighthouse District: Denmark’s Green Innovations in Herning	7/10/2024	1,204	110
SUPERSHINE joins the Network of Building Renovation Projects	9/2/2024	642	43
FB Launches Pilot Rewilding Project for SUPERSHINE to Transform Green Areas	11/12/2024	527	40
Co-Design Workshop: Engaging Youth Through Minecraft for Urban Design in Trieste	1/21/2025	309	21

Young Minds Shape Public Spaces: Co-Design Session in Trieste	1/28/2025	338	135
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4.1.3.3. Press Releases

Here is a table summarizing the outreach and engagement metrics for SUPERSHINE press releases, showcasing the impact and activities of the project.

Table 15 : SUPERSHINE Press Releases Outreach and Engagement

	Publication Date	Average Outreach	Average Engagement
A Closer Look into SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE: Get to know the impact better	12/18/2023	58	n/a
SUPERSHINE Project Holds Field Visit to See Energy Democracy in Action	12/10/2024	2,172	54

4.1.3.4. Video Interviews

Here is a table displaying the outreach and engagement metrics for SUPERSHINE video interviews, featuring key dialogues from the project series.

	Publication Date	Average Outreach	Average Engagement
SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE: Dialogues Under the Spotlight Series – Erdem Kocabey	1/15/2024	507	48
SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE: Dialogues Under the	1/15/2024	614	118

Spotlight Series – Riccardo Coletta			
SUPER-i & SUPERSHINE: Dialogues Under the Spotlight Series – Cristina Daví	1/24/2024	490	50

4.1.3.5. Event Releases

Event releases contribute significantly to the visibility of SUPERSHINE, supporting both outreach and engagement across communication channels.

ICONS regularly compiled a full list of events attended by partners on behalf of the project.

For each of these, tailored event releases were produced, creating additional impact on social media by enriching content shared through posts and updates.

Below is the list of event releases while the comprehensive list of all events attended can be found in the Annex.

It's also important to note that the SUPERSHINE website acts as an information hub for stakeholders, where not only project-specific activities but also sectoral and international events are showcased to raise awareness and connect with broader communities across Europe.

Table 16 : SUPERSHINE Event Releases Outreach and Engagement

	Publication Date	Average Outreach	Average Engagement
WORKSHOP: Investments in energy efficiency in public housing (with reference to Lighthouse Districts)	5/19/2023	73	n/a
New European Bauhaus in Regions and Cities	6/21/2023	79	n/a

European Week of Regions and Cities	11/9/2023	27	n/a
Satellite event: A national workspace on climate neutrality in cities	5/8/2024	18	n/a
New Bauhaus Stories	6/4/2024	3	n/a
NEB Lighthouse of Trieste Launch event	6/13/2024	675	68
INSME Annual Meeting: Unlocking Sustainable Finance for SMEs	10/14/2024	765	111
Transforming Social Housing Districts for a Sustainable Future	11/6/2024	382	33

4.1.3.6. Communication Effectiveness Tool

The figure below represents the communication effectiveness tool that is a strategic resource developed to support the refinement of SUPERSHINE’s communication and dissemination strategy.

By mapping publications across four quadrants—effective, reaching, engaging, and neutral—based on average outreach and engagement values, the tool enables the communication officers to identify the most impactful content formats, channels, and messages. It is designed not to benchmark SUPERSHINE among other projects but to support internal learning and continuous improvement, helping the team tailor future communication efforts for increased visibility and stakeholder interaction.

Figure 18 : SUPERSHINE Publication Effectiveness Quadrants

The publication effectiveness quadrant analysis below highlights clear distinctions in how different content types perform in terms of outreach and engagement.

- The journalistic article stands out as the most effective format, achieving exceptionally high average outreach and engagement, suggesting that in-depth, informative content resonates strongly with the targeted stakeholders, but also the general public.
- Video interviews also perform well, with notably high engagement despite more limited outreach, indicating their potential as powerful tools to connect with the SUPERSHINE audience.
- News releases, press releases, and event releases fall into a more neutral zone, providing consistent visibility but generating lower interaction.

These insights from the communication effectiveness tool suggest that future communication efforts could benefit from prioritizing articles and video interviews, while enhancing news, press and event releases with richer content and broader dissemination strategies.

4.1.4. Timeline

The timeline below covers the main activities for WP6 from M29 to the end of SUPERSHINE project.

When	What	Who
M29	Plan for Communication Dissemination Exploitation – Part II	ICONS
M30	2 nd Journalistic article – Starting production	ICONS
M31	Video production in Trieste	ICONS+APRE + ATER
	Newsletter #2	ICONS
M32	Policy Brief – Starting production	ICONS+APRE+DEMIR
M33	Newsletter #3	ICONS
M35	Infopacks – Starting production	ICONS +relevant partners
	Best Practice Book – Starting production	ICONS +relevant partners
M36	Newsletter #4	ICONS
M37	Article #2	ICONS
M38	Video release	ICONS
M39	Newsletter #5	ICONS
M40	Final event	ALL
M41	D6.4 DC Report D6.5 Exploitation plan	ICONS
	Newsletter #6	ICONS

Conclusions

The second version of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan for SUPERSHINE builds upon the initial strategy and CDE integrated approach, further refining it and ensuring alignment with the project's evolving goals. The plan enhances the solid foundation for the project's communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, grounded upon the identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and mapping of stakeholders.

The updated analysis of KERs and corresponding exploitation strategies highlights the diverse and innovative outcomes of the project, including the development of replicable models for smart districts based on energy efficiency, affordability, and sustainability. These outcomes aim to reduce energy poverty and accelerate the transition to zero-carbon living across Europe, focusing on sustainable social housing renovation, low-carbon mobility, and the integration of responsive technologies that optimize resources and promote well-being.

Communication activities reviewed in this report are continuously assessed and refined based on data and feedback, ensuring that SUPERSHINE's progress is effectively shared with all stakeholders. The plan's dynamic nature allows for the flexible adjustment of activities to keep them aligned with the project's goals and the needs of the communities it serves.

By maintaining this adaptive and strategic approach, SUPERSHINE is well-positioned to make a significant impact on social housing renovation, contribute to the European Green Deal, and support the transition to sustainable, zero-carbon living in Europe, with all ongoing activities set to be successfully completed in the final year of the project.

Annex

In addition to the event released above, SUPERSHINE partners participated to **31 events** (reaching more than thousands of participants).

Partner Short Name	Title of the event	Type of the event	Date	Place	Type audience	of	Size of audience
APRE/EEIP	ASK4Green: an Advocacy for Social Key-instances in the Green Transition	Conference	08/06/2023	Brussels	Scientific community, policy makers, civil society		50
APRE/HE/UoY	Affordable Housing Initiative Tech Camp 2023	Conference	08/06/2023	Barcelona	SH managers, NEB Community, Scientific community, policy makers, civil society		N/A
APRE	New European Bauhaus Awards 2023	Conference	22/06/2023	Brussels	NEB Community, Scientific community, policy makers, civil society		n/a
APRE	Grafting Cities" conference by Energy Cities Modena	Conference	18/10/2023	Modena	Scientific community, policy makers.		
APRE	Final Conference of the GREENROAD project	Conference	02/20/2024	Rome	NEB Community, Scientific community, policy makers, civil society		50
APRE	Recurring meetings for the establishment of the Italian national table on buildings energy efficiency	Conferences	April 2024 / Ongoing	Rome	Scientific community, policy makers		20

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APRE	Research Alliances for Climate-Neutral, Sustainable and Equitable Urban Communities . Event organised by ENEA and CNR under the framework of the CapaCITIES project.	Conference	26-27/2/2025	Rome	architects, engineers, scientific community, industry, policy makers, civil society, investors	>100
APRE	HYPOP project webinar 'Engaging Non-Technical Audiences: Best Practices for Energy' Communication'	webinar	20/3/2025	Online	architects, engineers, scientific community, industry, policy makers, civil society, investors, EU R&I actors	n/a
FællesBo	Training of caretakers in PV	Training	3/1/2025	Herning, DK	Caretakers	4
FællesBo	Training of caretakers in energy man.	Training	10/1/2024	Herning, DK	Caretakers	6
FællesBo	Training of caretakers in ECL manag.	Training	10/1/2024	Herning, DK	Caretakers	5
FællesBo	Training of caretakers in ECL manag.	Training	3/1/2025	Dep.19, Herning	Caretakers	5
FællesBo	Training of caretakers in ECL manag.	Training	4/1/2025	Dep.19, Herning	Caretakers	5
FællesBo	Training of caretakers in ECL manag.	Training	9/1/2025	Dep.24, Herning	Caretakers	5
FællesBo	Workshop for all FB staff-biodiver.	Workshop	2/2/2025	Herning, DK	FællesBo staff	100
FællesBo	Workshop in recycling	Workshop	10/1/2025	Dep.24, Herning	Volunteers in Oasis project	20
FællesBo	Event for residents on recycling	Training	2/1/2025	Dep.24, Herning	Residents	25

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FællesBo	Inauguration of Orangery-recycled	n/a	9/1/2025	Dep.24, Herning	Residents	35
FællesBo	Workshop on biodiversity	Workshop	10/1/2024	Dep.24, Herning	Volunteers in Oasis project	20
FællesBo	Event-organization board on sustainability	n/a	10/1/2024	Dep.20, Herning	Dep-board of teants	15
DEM	Hackathon for energy poverty in Edirne	Workshop	13/07/2024	Edirne Atatürk Kultur Merkezi	Students, Civil Society, Local governments	20
DEM	Sustainable Places 2024	Conference	23/09/2024	Luxembourg	Civil society, scientific community	30
DEM	Energy Poverty Workshop	Workshop	27/09/2024	Online	Civil society, scientific community, local government	12
ATER/APRE/UoY/ICONS	LAUNCH OF BOITO ACTIVITIES	Conference	13/06/2024	Trieste	architects, engineers, scientific community, industry, policy makers, civil society, investors	
APRE, ICONS, HE	EU Regions Week partner event "Transformation of social housing: inclusion and sustainability"	Conference	6/11/2024	Online	architects, engineers, scientific community, industry, policy makers, civil society, investors, EU R&I actors	50
AYMING	Sostenibilità e finanza agevolata: sinergie per l'impresa del domani (Sustainability and subsidized finance: synergies for the business o	Conference	10/24/2024	Milano	Industry, civil society, investors etc.	40

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EGC	UIA conference Copenhagen UIACPH2023	world in -	Conference	01/07/2023	Copenhagen	architects, engineers, scientific community, industry, policy makers, civil society, investors	65
EGC	Klimafolkemødet 2025 (People's Climate Meeting)	(People's Action	Fair	28/08/2025-30/08/2025	Middelfart, DK	architects, engineers, scientific community, industry, policy makers, civil society, investors	Approx. 40,000
INSME/UOY	Annual Meeting Unlocking Sustainable Finance for SMEs	Meeting	Conference	14-15/10/2024	Rome	architects, engineers, scientific community, industry, policy makers, civil society, investors	n/a
ALL	SUPER-i Final Event		Conference	14/11/2024	Copenhagen, DK	architects, engineers, scientific community, industry, policy makers, civil society, investors	30
ALL	SUPER-i final webinar "SUPER-i Legacy: Innovations and Impact for Sustainable Social Housing"	final "SUPER-i Legacy: Innovations and Impact for Sustainable Social Housing"	Webinar	2/13/2025	Online	architects, engineers, scientific community, industry, policy makers, civil society, investors	56

